

Optimized Design and Control of a Solar-Battery Powered BLDC Drive Using Ultra High-Gain Switched-Capacitor Boost Converter Ripple Reduction

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KEYWORDS

Solar energy,
Battery energy storage,
BLDC motor drive,
High gain switched capacitor
boost converter,
Incremental Conductance MPPT,
Bidirectional buck boost

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and control of a solar battery powered Brushless DC (BLDC) motor drive system utilizing an ultra high gain switched capacitor boost DC DC converter for efficient energy management and ripple current reduction. The proposed system integrates solar photovoltaic (PV) energy with a battery energy storage unit to ensure continuous and reliable power delivery to both the BLDC drive and associated DC loads. To extract maximum power from the PV source under varying irradiance conditions, an Incremental Conductance (INC) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is employed. The high gain switched capacitor boost converter minimizes source current ripple and reduces voltage stress on power devices, enhancing overall system efficiency and reliability. A bidirectional buck boost converter is used to manage battery charging and discharging operations, maintaining backup support during low solar availability. A double loop control strategy consisting of inner current and outer voltage control loops is implemented to regulate the DC bus voltage and ensure system stability. The entire system is modeled and validated using MATLAB Simulink, demonstrating effective power flow control, improved voltage regulation, and reduced ripple performance for electric drive and DC load applications.

I. Introduction

The increasing global demand for clean and sustainable energy has driven significant advancements in renewable energy-based power conversion technologies. According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean in its 2030 agenda under targets 7.1 and 7.2, there is an urgent call for clean and reliable renewable energy systems that can support the transformation of society, economies, and the environment. In line with this vision, the integration of solar photovoltaic energy with energy storage systems has become a promising approach to enhance reliability and independence in electrical systems, especially for electric drive applications and DC-powered loads [1], [2]. In recent years, the Brushless DC motor has gained significant importance in electric vehicle propulsion, industrial automation, and household appliances due to its high efficiency, compact design, and reduced maintenance compared to brushed motors [3], [4]. However, ensuring a stable and regulated DC bus voltage to drive BLDC motors using renewable energy sources presents critical challenges due to the intermittent nature of solar irradiance and the variable power demand from loads [5]. To address these issues, advanced power electronic converters with intelligent control strategies are necessary to maintain voltage regulation, reduce current ripple, and efficiently manage energy flow between the sources and the load [6], [7]. Among the various DC-DC converter topologies used in renewable energy applications, non-isolated step-up converters are widely adopted due to their simple structure and compact design. However, conventional converters such as the basic boost converter are limited in terms of voltage gain, especially at moderate duty ratios, and they suffer from high switching stress, poor efficiency, and elevated source current ripple [8], [9]. Several topologies have been proposed to overcome these limitations, including interleaved boost converters, coupled inductor-based converters, and converters with active and passive voltage lift techniques [10], [11]. Coupled inductor-based converters offer high voltage gain by adjusting the magnetic turns ratio, but they inherently suffer from leakage inductance and increased peak voltage stress, which deteriorate the overall efficiency and reliability of the system [12]. Moreover, these converters typically lack a common ground reference, making their integration into grounded

systems and EMI-sensitive environments problematic [13], [14]. Modified interleaved and split-duty boost converters have been suggested to address extended switch conduction intervals and output ripple, yet the output voltage support from capacitors over extended load durations remains a challenge [15], [16]. In response to these challenges, switched-capacitor-based DC-DC converters have gained popularity due to their ability to achieve high voltage gain without relying on magnetic coupling. These converters can operate at moderate duty ratios while reducing the stress on switching devices and minimizing the input current ripple [17], [18]. The use of diode-capacitor voltage lift techniques has further enhanced the performance of such converters by boosting the output voltage and reducing switching losses. Quadratic boost converters that integrate switched-capacitor cells have been shown to provide superior voltage gains with moderate component counts, making them highly suitable for low-input-voltage renewable energy systems [19], [20]. Despite these advancements, certain challenges remain in optimizing the overall system performance. Many existing converters have high component counts or elevated switch current stress, and some configurations still lack a common ground. To address these limitations, this work proposes an ultra high gain switched capacitor boost converter integrated with an inductor filter to reduce source current ripple and ensure absolute grounding, making it suitable for BLDC motor drives in green energy-powered systems [21], [22]. The proposed system integrates solar photovoltaic energy with a battery storage unit using a bidirectional buck boost converter that manages battery charge and discharge cycles. This enables the system to maintain uninterrupted power delivery to both the BLDC motor and connected DC loads, even during periods of low solar irradiance. To maximize energy harvesting, the Incremental Conductance Maximum Power Point Tracking algorithm is employed, providing fast and accurate tracking under dynamic environmental conditions [23]. A double loop control strategy consisting of an inner current loop and an outer voltage loop is implemented to regulate the DC bus voltage, improve dynamic response, and enhance overall system stability [24], [25]. This paper presents the complete design, control, and performance evaluation of the proposed solar battery powered BLDC drive system. The

entire system is modeled and validated using MATLAB Simulink, demonstrating significant improvements in voltage regulation, ripple current reduction, and power flow control under variable load and source conditions. The combination of high gain conversion, intelligent energy management, and advanced control strategy makes the proposed architecture a strong candidate for reliable green energy-powered motor drive systems and DC microgrids.

II. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The proposed system integrates a solar photovoltaic (PV) source and a battery energy storage system to ensure a continuous and stable supply for a Brushless DC (BLDC) motor and associated DC load. The solar PV module acts as the primary power source, and an Incremental Conductance (INC) Maximum Power Point

Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is used to extract maximum power under varying irradiance. The PV output is fed to an ultra high gain switched capacitor boost DC-DC converter, which steps up the voltage efficiently while minimizing source current ripple and voltage stress. An input inductor further reduces ripple and stabilizes input current. A bidirectional buck-boost converter connects the battery, managing its charge and discharge cycles based on energy availability and load demand as shown in Fig.1. A double loop control strategy, comprising an inner current loop and an outer voltage loop, is applied to regulate the DC bus voltage and maintain system stability. The controlled DC output powers the BLDC motor via an inverter and supports additional DC loads, ensuring reliable performance under dynamic operating conditions.

Fig. 1 Proposed system configuration solar and battery storage system for BLDC motor drive

III. Modeling and designing of solar configuration with high gain DC-DC converter

A. Solar PV Configuration

The solar PV module generates low-level DC voltage, typically 12V to 48V, depending on environmental conditions. To match this to high-voltage loads, an ultra high-gain DC-DC converter is used as shown in Fig.3. This converter operates in multiple switching modes, commonly based on Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM) and Discontinuous Conduction Mode (DCM). The key energy transfer process begins when the switch is turned ON, where the input inductor stores energy from the PV source. Capacitors are charged through a

configured diode-capacitor-switched structure, enhancing voltage in stages. When the switches turn off the inductors release stored energy through the diode-capacitor ladder network toward the output. The key voltage-boosting mechanism is achieved through switched-capacitor voltage lift, where capacitors are arranged in series to sum their voltages. Each stage adds a fraction of the input voltage based on the previous stage's voltage, resulting in a quadratic or cubic boost profile. The output voltage is then filtered by an output capacitor to provide a stable high DC voltage to the load.

a. PV Output Current Equation:

Fig. 2 equivalent model of PV solar.

$$I_{pv} = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{q(V_{pv} + I_{pv}R_s)}{nkT}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V_{pv} + I_{pv}R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

- I_{ph} : Photogenerated current
- I_0 : Reverse saturation current
- V_{PV} : PV voltage
- R_s, R_{sh} : Series and shunt resistance
- n : Ideality factor
- T : Temperature (K), q : Electron charge, k : Boltzmann constant

B. High-Gain Switched-Capacitor Boost Converter

The Switched-Capacitor Quadratic Boost Converter (SCQBC) is designed to achieve ultra-high voltage gain with low component stress and reduced ripple current, making it ideal for solar-powered BLDC motor drive systems. The operation of the converter is analyzed in two key modes: Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM) and Discontinuous Conduction Mode (DCM), depending on the inductor current continuity during the switching cycle. In CCM operation, two distinct sub-modes exist within one switching period: Mode 1, where both switches S1 and S2 are ON (active interval), and Mode 2, where both switches are OFF (freewheeling interval). During Mode 1, initiated at time t_0 , the input voltage V_i is directly applied across inductor L1, while L2 receives voltage from the charged capacitor C1. This can be expressed using:

Fig.3 solar system configuration of ultra high gain switched capacitor DC-DC boost converter

$$V_{L1} = V_i \quad (2)$$

$$V_{L2} = V_{C1} \quad (3)$$

In Mode 2, which starts at t_1 when switches are turned OFF, inductor L1 along with the input source charges the capacitor C1, and the energy from L2 along with capacitors C3 and C0 supplies power to the load. The voltages across inductors are now:

$$V_{L1} = V_i - V_{C1} \quad (4)$$

$$V_{L2} = V_{C1} + V_{C3} - V_0 \quad (5)$$

To analyze the steady-state performance, the volt-second balance principle is applied to the inductors. This leads to the derivation of the capacitor voltages:

$$V_{C1} = V_i(1 - D) \quad (6)$$

$$V_{C2} = V_i(1 - D)^2 \quad (7)$$

$$3V_{C3} = V_i(2 - D)(1 - D)^2 \quad (8)$$

Here, D is the duty ratio. From these capacitor voltages, the overall voltage gain of the converter in CCM can be derived as:

$$G_{CCM} = \frac{V_0}{V_i} = \frac{3-D}{(1-D)^2} \quad (9)$$

This formula highlights the quadratic nature of the converter, achieving high voltage gain at moderate duty ratios, which is ideal for stepping up low PV voltages (e.g., 24 V) to high levels (e.g., 400–600 V). To determine the current stress on components, the peak current of inductor L2 during Mode 1 and Mode 2 is calculated as:

$$(IL_{2p})_I = \frac{V_{C1}}{L_2} DT_s \quad (10)$$

$$(IL_{2p})_{II} = \frac{V_0 - V_{C1} - V_{C3}}{L_2} D_x T_s \quad (11)$$

Equating these two peak currents at the switching boundary ensures smooth operation:

$$(IL_{2p})_I = (IL_{2p})_{II} \quad (12)$$

From this, the effective duty ratio in DCM D_x is derived:

$$D_x = \frac{D(1-D)\left(\frac{V_0}{V_i}\right)}{(1-D)^2 - (3-2D)} \quad (13)$$

In DCM operation, when the inductor current drops to zero before the start of the next switching cycle, the load is solely supplied by the output capacitor C0. The current through capacitor C0 is:

$$I_{C0} = \left(\frac{1}{2} D_x IL_{2p2}\right) - I_0 \quad (14)$$

By setting the average value of IC0 to zero for steady state, and substituting the inductor current and duty ratio expressions, the DCM voltage gain can also be derived.

C. Incremental Conductance MPPT algorithm

The Incremental Conductance (INC) method is based on the fact that the derivative of power with respect to voltage is zero at the maximum power point (MPP), positive to the left of MPP, and negative to the right as shown in Fig.4.

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = \frac{d(IV)}{dV} = I + V \frac{dI}{dV} \quad (15)$$

- At MPP: $\frac{dP}{dV} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{dI}{dV} = -\frac{I}{V}$ (16)

- Left of MPP: $\frac{dI}{dV} > -\frac{I}{V} \Rightarrow \frac{dP}{dV} > 0$ (17)

- Right of MPP: $\frac{dI}{dV} < -\frac{I}{V} \Rightarrow \frac{dP}{dV} < 0$ (18)

Algorithm Steps:

1. Measure $I(k)$ and $V(k)$
2. Compute $\Delta I = I(k) - I(k - 1)$, $\Delta V(k) = V(k) - V(k - 1)$
3. If $\Delta V = 0$
 - If $\Delta I = 0$: MPP reached \rightarrow No change
 - If $\Delta I > 0$: Left of Mpp \rightarrow Decrease voltage (decrease duty)
 - If $\Delta I < 0$: Right of MPP \rightarrow Increase voltage (increase duty)
4. $\Delta V \neq 0$
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} = -\frac{I}{V}$: MPP
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} > -\frac{I}{V}$: Left of Mpp \rightarrow Decrease duty
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} < -\frac{I}{V}$: Right of MPP \rightarrow Increase duty

Fig. 4. Flow chart of INC algorithm of MPPT for solar conversion.

IV. Designing of Bidirectional DC-DC Buck-Boost Converter for BESS

In the proposed solar-battery powered BLDC drive system, the bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter is responsible for managing energy flow between the battery and the DC bus based on solar availability and load requirements as shown in Fig.5. This converter operates in two primary modes: charging (buck mode) and discharging (boost mode). In the charging mode, when the solar panel output voltage V_{PV} is greater than the battery voltage V_{bat} , excess energy from the solar source is used to charge the battery. Here, the converter functions in buck mode, stepping down the DC bus voltage V_{dc} to suit the charging profile of the battery. The main switch (S1) is controlled using PWM signals and the inductor charges when S1 is ON, transferring energy to the battery when S1 is OFF through a diode path. The battery charging voltage is given by:

Fig.5 battery energy storage system configuration

$$V_{bat} = D \cdot V_{dc} \quad (19)$$

In the discharging mode, the system experiences reduced solar generation or high load demand, and the converter switches to boost mode, drawing power from the battery to maintain a constant DC bus voltage V_{dc} . This occurs when V_{bat} is less than V_{dc} . In this case, the other switch (S2) is operated using PWM control. When S2 is ON, energy is stored in the inductor from the battery, and when it is OFF, this stored energy is transferred to the DC bus. The output voltage of the converter during this mode is given by:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_{bat}}{1-D} \quad (20)$$

This bidirectional operation ensures smooth charging and discharging, stabilizing the DC bus voltage required for efficient operation of the BLDC motor and other DC loads, even under varying solar irradiance conditions.

A. Control designing of BESS

In the proposed solar-battery powered BLDC motor drive system, the double-loop PI control strategy is employed to ensure robust and precise regulation of the DC bus voltage while maintaining system stability during dynamic load and source variations. The control architecture is divided into two cascaded loops: an outer voltage control loop and an inner current control loop. The outer loop is responsible for maintaining the DC bus voltage V_{dc} at the desired reference level V_{dc}^{ref} , by generating a current reference I_{ref} for the inner loop. The voltage controller operates based on the voltage error $e_v(t)$, which is defined as the difference between the reference voltage and the actual measured voltage:

Fig. 6 Proposed energy management strategy for the BESS

$$e_v(t) = V_{dc}^{ref}(t) - V_{dc}(t) \quad (21)$$

This error is processed through a PI (Proportional-Integral) controller, whose output becomes the current reference:

$$I_{ref}(t) = K_{pv} \cdot e_v(t) + K_{iv} \cdot \int e_v(t) dt \quad (22)$$

The inner current loop compares this reference current I_{ref} with the actual current I_{dc} flowing through the inductor or to the load. The resulting error is used by the current PI controller to determine the appropriate duty cycle for the converter's switching devices, ensuring that the actual current follows the reference accurately even under rapidly changing load conditions.

Current Error:

$$e_i(t) = I_{ref}(t) - I_{dc}(t) \quad (23)$$

PI Current Controller Output (duty ratio control):

$$D(t) = K_{pi} \cdot e_i(t) + K_{ii} \cdot \int e_i(t) dt \quad (24)$$

Here, K_{pv} and K_{iv} are the proportional and integral gains of the voltage controller, while K_{pi} and K_{ii} are the gains for the current controller. This hierarchical control scheme enables fast dynamic current control and accurate voltage regulation, making it suitable for

renewable energy-fed systems like the BLDC motor drive in your design.

V. Controller and Designing of BLDC motor drive

The BLDC motor relies on the correct sequencing of voltages to stator windings based on rotor position feedback. Hall sensors detect the rotor position and enable the switching of the inverter such that the generated stator magnetic field leads the rotor field, producing continuous torque as shown in Fig.7. The inverter operates in a six-step commutation pattern where two phases conduct at any instant, and one remains off. This pattern ensures trapezoidal current waveforms synchronized with the back EMF. As the rotor rotates, the back EMF varies, and the controller continuously adjusts the applied voltage and current. This coordinated control of voltage, current, and commutation angle ensures efficient and smooth operation of the motor under varying loads and supply conditions.

Fig.7 BLDC motor drive configuration

A. Designing of BLDC Motor

The Brushless DC (BLDC) motor is an electronically commutated machine where the stator is energized in a specific sequence to produce a rotating magnetic field, and the rotor follows due to permanent magnets. The motor exhibits trapezoidal back EMF and is often controlled based on rotor position feedback using Hall Effect sensors. The BLDC motor's electrical dynamics are governed by Kirchhoff's voltage law applied to each stator winding. For a three-phase, star-connected BLDC motor, the voltage equations for each phase are:

$$V_a = Ri_a + L \frac{di_a}{dt} + e_a \quad (25)$$

$$V_b = Ri_b + L \frac{di_b}{dt} + e_b \quad (26)$$

$$V_c = Ri_c + L \frac{di_c}{dt} + e_c \quad (27)$$

Where:

- $V_{a,b,c}$: Terminal voltages of phases a, b, and c
- $i_{a,b,c}$: Phase currents
- R : Resistance per phase
- L : Inductance per phase
- $e_{a,b,c}$: Back EMFs of each phase

The back EMF for each phase is dependent on the rotor electrical angle θ and angular velocity ω , and for a BLDC motor, it follows a trapezoidal profile:

$$e_a = K_e \cdot f_a(\theta) \cdot \omega \quad (28)$$

$$e_b = K_e \cdot f_b(\theta) \cdot \omega \quad (29)$$

$$e_c = K_e \cdot f_c(\theta) \cdot \omega \quad (30)$$

Where K_e is the back EMF constant and $f_{a,b,c}(\theta)$ are trapezoidal functions depending on rotor position sensed using Hall sensors.

B. Mechanical Modeling of BLDC Motor

The rotor dynamics follow Newton's second law of motion, balancing the electromagnetic torque with the load and frictional torque. The mechanical equation is:

$$J \cdot \frac{d\omega}{dt} + B \cdot \omega = T_e - T_L \quad (31)$$

Where:

- J : Rotor moment of inertia
- B : Friction coefficient
- ω : Rotor angular speed (rad/s)
- T_e : Electromagnetic torque
- T_L : Load torque

The electromagnetic torque generated by the BLDC motor is a function of the back EMF and the current in each phase:

$$T_e = \frac{1}{\omega} (e_a i_a + e_b i_b + e_c i_c) \quad (32)$$

This shows that torque is directly proportional to the product of back EMF and stator current.

B. PI-Based Speed Controller for BLDC Motor

In a BLDC motor drive system powered by a solar and battery energy source, precise speed regulation is critical for dynamic performance and efficient operation. This is achieved using a double-loop control architecture, where an outer speed control loop governs the motor speed and an inner current control loop regulates the motor current. The outer loop uses a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller that receives the difference between the reference speed $\omega^*(t)$ and the actual rotor speed $\omega(t)$ as feedback. This speed error, denoted by $e_\omega(t)$, is computed as:

Fig.8 speed controller designing of BLDC motor drive

$$e_\omega(t) = \omega^*(t) - \omega(t) \quad (33)$$

The PI controller then processes this error to generate the reference current $i_{ref}^*(t)$, which corresponds to the required electromagnetic torque needed to achieve the desired speed. The PI controller transfer function is:

$$G_{PI}(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} \quad (34)$$

Where K_p is the proportional gain and K_i is the integral gain. The controller output in time domain is:

$$i_{ref}^*(t) = K_p \cdot e_\omega(t) + K_i \cdot \int e_\omega(t) dt \quad (35)$$

This reference current is fed into the inner current control loop, which uses a hysteresis current controller or PWM to generate switching signals for the inverter. The inverter, based on the switching pattern and rotor position signals from Hall sensors, commutates the stator windings appropriately to produce a rotating magnetic field that drives the rotor. The electromagnetic torque generated by the BLDC motor is directly proportional to the phase current and is modeled as:

$$T_e(t) = K_t \cdot i(t) \quad (36)$$

Where K_t is the torque constant of the motor. The torque produced drives the motor shaft, and the mechanical behavior is governed by Newton's second law for rotational motion:

$$J \cdot \frac{d\omega(t)}{dt} + B \cdot \omega(t) = T_e(t) - T_L(t) \quad (37)$$

Here, J is the moment of inertia, B is the damping coefficient, and $T_L(t)$ is the load torque. To ensure stable and fast speed response, the PI controller gains K_p and K_i are designed by analyzing the transfer function of the open-loop system from current to speed:

$$\frac{\omega(s)}{i(s)} = \frac{K_t}{J_s + B} \quad (38)$$

Combining the plant and PI controller, the closed-loop speed transfer function becomes:

$$\frac{\omega(s)}{\omega^*(s)} = \frac{(K_p s + K_i) \cdot K_t}{(J_s + B)s + (K_p s + K_i) \cdot K_t} \quad (39)$$

This function is used for controller tuning to ensure desired closed-loop performance in terms of settling time, overshoot, and steady-state error. The control system ensures that the motor can track the reference speed accurately despite variations in load torque or input voltage from the solar-battery system.

VI. Simulation Results and Discussion

The proposed solar and battery-powered BLDC motor drive system was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink for a total duration of 1 second to evaluate its dynamic performance and power-sharing capability under varying environmental and load conditions. The system includes an 8 kW solar photovoltaic array, a 5 kW battery energy storage system, a 2 kW BLDC motor, and a 3.2 kW DC load. The solar power is extracted using a high-gain DC-DC boost converter integrated with the Incremental Conductance (INC) MPPT algorithm to ensure maximum power harvesting under all irradiance levels. Initially, from 0 to 0.2 seconds, the solar irradiance is maintained at 1000 W/m², allowing the solar system to operate at peak capacity. During this period, the BLDC motor, DC load, and battery charging are fully supported by solar power. As the irradiance drops from 1000 W/m² to 500 W/m² between 0.2 and 0.3 seconds, solar power generation decreases, and the battery begins to discharge to compensate for the power deficit, thereby maintaining uninterrupted power supply to both the motor and DC load. Between 0.3 and 0.4 seconds, the irradiance further decreases from 500 W/m² to 300 W/m², reducing the solar output even more. The battery discharge rate increases accordingly to sustain the load demand and ensure system reliability. During the critical period from 0.4 to 0.5 seconds, the irradiance drops to 0 W/m², and no solar power is generated. At this point, the battery alone supplies power to the entire system, effectively supporting both the motor and DC load without compromising performance. Throughout this duration, the system dynamically balances power from solar and battery sources while maintaining a stable DC bus voltage. Simultaneously, the BLDC motor undergoes variable speed operation to test the system's stability and controller response. From 0 to 0.5 seconds, the motor speed is held constant at 1000 RPM. From 0.5 to 0.65 seconds, the speed is ramped up from 1000 to 1500 RPM, followed by another increment to 2000 RPM between 0.65 and 0.85 seconds. Finally, from 0.85 to 1 second, the

motor speed further increases to 3000 RPM. Despite these sharp changes in mechanical speed and load conditions, the proposed control strategy ensures smooth operation, effective torque response, and minimal overshoot. The bidirectional DC-DC converter effectively manages battery charge and discharge, ensuring constant power delivery under all test scenarios as shown in Fig.9. Overall, the simulation results confirm that the system maintains stability, reliable power sharing, and consistent motor performance, even during rapid irradiance fluctuations and dynamic speed transitions.

Fig.9. Simulation results of Dynamic Performance Analysis of Solar-Battery Powered BLDC Drive under Varying Irradiance and Speed Conditions

VII. Conclusion

An optimized solar-battery powered BLDC motor drive system has been successfully designed and analyzed using an ultra high-gain switched-capacitor boost converter with ripple reduction capabilities. The integration of solar PV with battery energy storage ensures continuous and reliable power delivery to both the BLDC drive and the associated DC loads, even under dynamically changing solar irradiance conditions. The use of the Incremental Conductance (INC) MPPT algorithm allows efficient maximum power extraction from the PV source, while the proposed converter significantly reduces source current ripple and device voltage stress, thereby improving overall system efficiency and robustness. The implementation of a bidirectional buck-boost converter ensures stable battery charging and discharging operation, enabling seamless power balancing between solar and storage sources. Furthermore, the double-loop control strategy effectively regulates the DC bus voltage through coordinated voltage and current control, contributing to improved dynamic performance and system stability. Simulation results obtained in MATLAB/Simulink validate the system's ability to handle varying speed commands and load demands while maintaining constant power flow and voltage regulation. This work demonstrates that the proposed configuration is a reliable and efficient solution for renewable-powered electric drive and DC load applications.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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